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INITIAL EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS OF DAMPING DUE TO LIQUID SLOSHING IN A SCALED AIRCRAFT WING MODEL

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Abstract: Fuel sloshing inside aircraft wings can potentially increase the net damping of the wing structure. Building upon previous work on simpler sloshing systems, we present a scaled research wing prototype equipped with a fuel tank that allows the observation of liquid sloshing and quantification of induced dynamic effects. Experiments were conducted at 50% filling level and the equivalent dry case with frozen mass. We demonstrate substantial additional damping effects in multiple frequency components when liquid is added inside the tank. The dissipative effect is most noticeable in the first frequency component with deformations typical of the first bending mode of the structure, as the damping ratio was found to be substantially increased in the sloshing case regardless of the amplitude of motion.

NOMENCLATURE

ϕ_j	Phase of the nonlinear signal component j	N_S	Bin sliding size in the NLS analysis
ζ_j	Damping ratio of the nonlinear signal component j	N_W	Time bin size in the NLS analysis
A_j	Amplitude of the nonlinear signal component j	T_j	Natural period of vibration mode j
F_j	Natural frequency of vibration mode j	y	Original signal
f_j	Frequency of the nonlinear signal component j	y_e	Fitted function
M	Number of frequency components in the NLS analysis	y_e^k	Fitted function in time bin k

1 INTRODUCTION

Aircraft designed and developed in the European zone must comply with the certification specifications of the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA). According to the Certification Specifications for Large Aeroplanes (CS-25) Acceptable Means of Compliance (AMC), the structural dynamic model of the aircraft may include damping information: “*In the absence of better information it will normally be acceptable to assume 0.03 (i.e. 1.5% equivalent critical viscous damping) for all flexible modes. Structural damping may be increased over the 0.03 value to be consistent with the high structural response levels caused by extreme gust intensity, provided justification is given.*” [1]. The value of the structural damping may be increased if justified and a larger value of structural damping may lead to a less conservative structural design through

reduction of the peak loads and/ or improving the fatigue life of certain components. These improvements in turn lead to a more efficient use of materials, reduced weight and improved fuel burn, in line with the current trends towards a reduction in the environmental impact of aviation (e.g. the ATAG net-zero carbon goal by 2050¹).

The classical approach for aircraft loads alleviation are active methods making use of control surfaces or spoilers, actuated using an active control law to reduce the dynamic response of the aircraft to gusts and manoeuvres. More recently there have been proposals of passive loads alleviation using tow-steered composites [2] or folding wing-tips [3]. Another possible candidate for reductions in aircraft dynamic loads is fuel sloshing inside wings, taking into account and exploiting the movement of the fuel. A net increase in damping may be achieved due to the dynamic interaction between the moving fuel and the wing structure. This work is part of the Sloshing Wing Dynamics (SLOWD), an EU-funded project² aiming to investigate and exploit fuel sloshing in order to increase the effective damping in aircraft structures.

The experimental work presented here is based on extensive previous investigations into systems of reduced complexity. A transient single degree of freedom analysis was conducted in [4], where an experimental analysis supported by two numerical models of various fidelity showed that (1) vertical sloshing induces substantial damping effects that depend on the tank filling level and amplitude of excitation and (2) qualitatively and quantitatively different sloshing dissipation mechanisms are present at large and small amplitudes of excitation. Similar findings were reported in [5]. An in-depth experimental and numerical analysis based on single-frequency harmonic excitation [6,7] then revealed how the liquid movements relative to the tank affect the observed induced effects.

Using the insights and analysis developed in the previous studies, this work represent a step up in the analysis complexity considering the liquid sloshing induced effects in a scaled research wing prototype. The research methodology is presented in Section 2 and the experimental results concerning the dry and wet structure are presented and discussed in Sections 3 & 4. Conclusions and future directions of work are presented in Section 5.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

The experimental demonstrator called “MiniWoT” is shown in Figure 1. The main structural part is composed of two spars and five torque tubes with spanwise varying cross-sectional properties to match the static and dynamic response of a full scale research prototype wing specimen as described in [8]. The 1:5 scale structure is approximately 3 meters long and is cantilevered at the root to a strong wall using a wedge-bracket configuration that enables the modification of the specimen dihedral angle (shown here in 0° dihedral configuration). On top of the main structural part there is a transparent fuel tank with scaled geometry. The tank bears only part of the loads and it is partially decoupled from the main structural part using two rigid connection points and five flexure-type connections that allow for limited spanwise relative motion between the tank and the underlying structure. This configuration was chosen with multiple aims in mind, among the most important: (1) achieve scaled natural frequencies and mode shapes, (2) allow for the liquid flow observation inside the tank from the lateral and top directions and (3) the tank should have set scaled dimensions and spanwise position, representative of the full-scale specimen. It can easily be seen how such requirements impose certain design constraints

¹<https://www.atag.org/component/news/?view=pressrelease&id=125>, accessed on 27.05.2022

²https://slowd-project.eu/project/project_overview, accessed on 27.05.2022

that move the fuel tank vertically up from its natural position inside the wing as well as raising considerable challenges concerning the connection points between the tank and the underlying structure.

The fuel tank has a geometry representative of the full-scale prototype with 8 interior cells separated by the baffles. The 7 baffles are removable and multiple baffle geometries can be studied. The individual cells can also be sealed using the solid-section baffles without perforations – this case is considered in this work.

Figure 1: MiniWoT scaled test specimen. Top figure: (1) – Cantilever to the strong wall connection, (2) – Scaled structure model, (3) – Scaled fuel tank model and (4) – Loading points for step release tests. Bottom figure: Instrumentation layout

The structure is instrumented using 14 accelerometers, one vertical displacement measurement at the tip trailing edge, strain gauges at the root and two high frame rate video cameras for the observation of the sloshing liquid from the side and top of the tank. Three of the accelerometers were placed on the tank in three different spanwise positions as shown in Figure 1 and labeled “tank tip”, “mid” and “root”. Two removable eye-bolts (marked with (4) in Figure 1) and a pulley – chain hoist mechanism are used for loading the structure vertically downward after which it is released into free decaying motion using a pin-release mechanism.

The experimental test plan included but was not limited to the following:

- Ground vibration tests with and without tank attached, part of which were presented in [8]
- Step release tests without liquid (dry tests), with and without additional mass to account for the “frozen” liquid

- Step release tests with tap water as the working liquid, with and without added dye
- Studies with and without the baffles, with the baffles of different solidity ratios
- Studies with varying filling levels.

In this work we present an initial assessment and interpretation of the experimental results concerning step release tests at 0° dihedral angle, with 50% water filling level in each individual sealed cell using solid-section baffles, and the dynamically equivalent dry case with added mass to account for the "frozen" liquid. Each test was conducted at least three times to assess its repeatability. All frequency and time information was normalized to the first bending mode frequency for confidentiality purposes.

2.1 Nonlinear system identification

The transient MiniWoT experimental responses considered in this work exhibit moderately non-linear stiffness effects and highly nonlinear induced damping; due to these characteristics, the system identification problem is not trivial. Many nonlinear system identification techniques have classically been proposed and used, e.g. based on the Volterra series or block-structured nonlinear models consisting of interconnected linear and nonlinear subsystems [9]. Due to the nature of the problem at hand, piecewise linear modelling is adopted here. Such approaches assume time-localised linear behaviour, allowing the application of well-known linear techniques on the short sections of the time-domain response of the studied nonlinear system. This strategy was shown to adequately represent nonlinear systems as long as the nonlinearities are smooth [10]. The piecewise linear system can be found using the fitting techniques which minimize the distance between the signal and chosen fitting functions in a least square sense. Such methods belong to a class of Nonlinear Least Squares (NLS) fitting techniques and have been successfully used in the past for the analysis of one dominant frequency component in beam sloshing experiments [11]. We extend the NLS analysis here to cover all major frequency components of the transient signals. A description of the method as we use it here is offered next.

Let $F1$ be the natural frequency of vibration of the first bending mode of the MiniWoT structure, as identified by studying the small amplitude vibrations of the structure. The time-dependent acceleration data $y(t)$ contains 75 samples of data per period of motion $T1 = 1/F1$. The size of the data bin is chosen to be $N_W = 150$ samples, corresponding to 2 periods of motion of the first vibration mode of the structure. A classical damped multi-harmonic motion representation

$$y_e = \sum_{j=1}^M \left[A_j \exp(-\zeta_j \omega_j t) \cos(\omega_j \sqrt{1 - \zeta_j^2} t + \phi_j) \right] \quad (1)$$

is fitted to the signal inside each data bin in a least squares sense, where M is the number of frequency components considered to be dominant in the step release response. Each signal component j is characterised by its amplitude A_j , damping ratio ζ_j , frequency ω_j and phase ϕ_j . Figure 2 exemplifies this methodology, showing the signal binning and decomposition. The black curve represents the original signal $y(t)$. Starting from $t = 0$, a bin of length N_W is selected, an estimate $y_e(t_1)$ is obtained for bin number 1 using M signal components and then the bin slides by N_S samples, after which the procedure is repeated. The signal at time t_k will thus be described by the function $y_e^k(t)$. The length of the sliding distance N_S establishes the time resolution of the analysis and is chosen such that each frequency component of interest can be

Figure 3: Example of NLS identification result. Original signal is shown with black and fitted functions are shown with coloured curves.

3. If the damping ratio of one component ζ_j exceeds a threshold value (set here at 0.9, or 90% of critical damping), the respective component is eliminated from the signal estimate y_e for all subsequent bins.

As it can be seen, these constraints do not limit the search space excessively. Constraint #1 ensures that no amplitude exceeds two times the initial acceleration at the step release time; note that physically there is no reason why any component should reach such values in free vibrations. Constraint #2 ensures that the identified frequency component will be found in the relative vicinity ($\pm 10\%$ was used here) of the linear estimate, while still allowing for significant nonlinear effects to be manifested by the shifts in frequency. This constraint makes the tracking and post-processing of each frequency component easier. Note also that for the well-separated frequency components this constraint can be relaxed or eliminated completely. Finally, constraint #3 is instrumental in the robustness and stability of the algorithm. It was observed that, when the component j has negligibly small presence in the signal in the bin number k , the returned values for both $A_j(k)$ and $\zeta_j(k)$ increase steeply. Of course, a local increase does not affect the other components since the j -th amplitude is very low at this point anyway. However, if left unchecked, it immediately leads to ever increasing parameter values and oscillations in the solution which then affect the stability of the analysis. The threshold of $\zeta = 0.9$ is well above the expected damping ratios for any frequency component, such that it does not over-constrain the analysis.

The residuals for each fitted function are computed as

$$Res(y_e) = y(t) - y_e(t) \quad (2)$$

and the sum of squares of the residuals (SSR) in a bin is

Figure 4: Example of residuals and summed squared residuals for the fitted functions shown in Figure 3

$$Res2(y_e) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_W} \left(y(t) - y_e(t) \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

with the units of gravity squared. An example of residuals for this analysis are shown in Figure 4 for the fitting case shown in Figure 3. Figure 4(a) shows the residuals for the first fitted function immediately after $t = 0$ for each sample inside the bin of length N_W , while Figure 4(b) shows the SSR values for all data bins, e.g. the first point represents the SSR for the bin shown in Figure 4(a). Residuals of approximately 10% of the maximum acceleration value can be seen in the first fitted bin and the squared residuals are dropping together with the amplitude of the signal, as expected. The fitting error is largest in the first cycle of motion, due to the very rich frequency content following immediately after the step release event. Such values for the residuals are common for this type of piecewise linear analysis [10]. Correlating these results with the qualitative view in Figure 3, we conclude that this method offers an adequate representation of the transient system.

Before moving to the results section, it is important to discuss one possible limitation of the damping ratio identification *specifically* in extremely nonlinear circumstances. The damping ratio of any specific physical system may exhibit amplitude-dependent nonlinearities such that the values ζ_j change substantially (nonlinearly) within the duration of a single data bin, i.e. one or two periods of motion in this case. Even though there is no indication that this might be the case with the present system, it is important to note that because of the linear response assumption within any single data bin (implying a constant ζ_j), the choice of the size of the bin N_W can lead to the averaging effect for the ζ_j values over multiple time instances. Consequently, the identified damping estimate may be weighted by the consecutive or neighbouring damping values in such highly nonlinear instances. It was found that a data bin of length less than two periods of motion of the lowest frequency leads to substantial oscillations in the solution. Consequently, we assume constant ζ_j values over any two periods of motion. There is thus a compromise to be made between the time resolution of the analysis and the stability and robustness of the damping estimates.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section considers the initial analysis conducted on the experimental data for the 50% filling level case with the sealed tank cells (solid section baffles that allow for no liquid communication

between the tank cells) and the dynamically equivalent dry structure case. We first assess the dynamic response typical of the large amplitude vibrations of the dry system and then investigate different aspects of the sloshing-induced effects.

Figure 5: Frequency-amplitude characteristic of the acceleration signal at the tip of the tank for the dry and 50% fill cases

Figure 6: The amplitude, frequency and damping ratio of the first frequency component (component 1) of the acceleration time series measured throughout the fuel tank, dry case

3.1 Large amplitude vibrations of the dry system

It is instructive to begin our analysis by assessing the frequency-amplitude characteristic of the transient response of the dry structure. Figure 5 shows the Fast Fourier Transform of the vertical acceleration response at the tip of the tank following the step release, computed over the first 20 periods of motion T_1 . The same characteristic is included for the wet case for reference. The frequency components that are seen to have the most significant contribution

to the transient signal are found in the vicinity of the normal modes corresponding to the first two out-plane bending modes (F1 and F2), first torsional mode F3 and a higher order out-plane bending mode F4. These first 4 signal components, selected by observing the amplitude of their contribution, are thus considered in the system identification process, and the corresponding frequency peaks identified in Figure 5 are named f_1 to f_4 . Another feature that can be observed in Figure 5 is the evidence of sidebands due to the nonlinear effects that manifest themselves as additional amplitude peaks, specifically at the frequencies offset by integer multiples of the one or multiple principal frequency components. In this case, an evidence of the f1 sidebands is immediately seen as indicated by the amplitude peaks marked by the dashed vertical lines. The exact cause of such sidebands in this case is unclear, but similar effects were observed in previous nonlinear studies [13]. However, awareness of their presence in the shown frequency-response characteristics will be useful in the subsequent detailed analysis of the fitted frequency components.

While the detailed analysis of the frequency components of the dry system will mainly be conducted in conjunction with the wet system, we take the opportunity here to investigate the robustness of the NLS procedure applied to this data. As shown in Figure 1, there are three accelerometers distributed across the length of the fuel tank. We apply the NLS procedure presented in Section 2 to the three accelerometer signals, for three test repetitions. Figure 6 shows a synthesis of the results that were obtained, namely the identified amplitude of component 1 A_1 , frequency f_1 (in Equation 1, $f_j = \omega_j/(2\pi)$) and damping ratio ζ_1 expressed as the percentage of critical damping. The mean values among the three repetitions are shown, together with the vertical bars showing minimum/ maximum deviations.

Figure 7: Typical sloshing response of the MiniWoT structure, 50% filling level case compared to dynamically equivalent dry case

Considering that the first component of the signal is dominated by the first modal contribution, the amplitude A_1 increases in value from the tank root to the tank tip, as expected. The identified frequency and damping ratio (middle and bottom of Figure 6) show consistent values regardless

of which accelerometer is used. The error bars are larger as we move from the tank tip towards the root, as the signal to noise ratio is reduced. For the frequency component dominated by the first bending mode, we would expect to find the same damping and frequency values regardless of the accelerometer position across the tank and this is indeed what we see. The results obtained are thus consistent and indicate robustness of the identification method. Similar results were obtained for the higher frequency components which will not be shown here due to the limited space but will be analysed in relation to the wet system.

3.2 Large amplitude vibrations of the wet system

Figure 8: Amplitude of component 1 vs normalized time, 50% filling level case and dynamically equivalent dry case. Error bars show the variability between test repetitions

Figure 9: Frequencies and damping ratios of component 1 vs component 1 acceleration amplitude, 50% filling level and dynamically equivalent dry case. Error bars show the variability between test repetitions. The amplitude decays following the step release event at A

For the wet analysis, the 50% filling level case is considered with the solid-section baffles. An initial overview of the differences between the dry and wet systems can be seen by inspecting

the tank tip acceleration versus time for the two cases. These results are shown in Figure 7, where the time parameter was normalized by T_1 . The mean values among the three repetitions are shown with the black curves and the red/ green bands indicate the minimum and maximum acceleration values. Insets are included showing the detailed views at selected times. The differences between the dry and wet cases in the first part of the transient are not noticeable. When the motion progresses, the amplitude of the wet system drops faster as a first indication of the induced damping effects due to sloshing. Similar trends were noted in simpler single degree of freedom transient sloshing tests [4]. There are also multiple frequency components noticeable immediately following the step release event which disappear from the acceleration signals at different rates between the dry and wet cases until only the first frequency component is dominant. Small phase shifts, which are indicative of frequency differences, can also be observed when comparing the dry and wet systems. These aspects can be investigated further by unpacking the signal into its components using the NLS procedure.

Figures 8 – 12 show the amplitudes, frequencies and damping ratios for the 4 acceleration components. Furthermore, since the damping ratios for the wet and dry cases are different, the same acceleration values will be reached at different times, so the frequency and damping values are shown as a function of the component amplitude for comparison purposes. The tank tip acceleration among the three repetitions was used for this analysis, the markers and error bars having the same significance as before.

Starting with the second half of the first period of motion, a distinct drop of component 1 amplitude can be seen in Figure 8 for the wet case when compared to the dry case. It is interesting that this is not immediately obvious by inspecting the complete timeseries in Figure 7, the reason being that component 1 of the signal conveys only fractional information about the overall motion characteristics in the first cycle of motion (5.5g of the 15g peak acceleration). Other frequency components of the signal are thus seen to be dominant in the first part of the transient response. An initial half-period delay is noticeable for the wet case A_1 amplitude to deviate and decrease below the dry response, this can be understood by studying these trends in conjunction with the liquid movement – this analysis will be conducted in Section 4. The differences in amplitude increase substantially afterwards, indicative of important sloshing-induced dissipative effects influencing the first out-plane bending component. Two points of interest are also emphasized in Figures 8 and 9: **A** represents the step release event and **B** represents the point in time when the wet system reaches $A_1 = 2.5g$.

The frequency variation trends are similar between the two cases, as seen at the top of Figure 9. Both vertical and horizontal error bars are now included, as there are small variations in both amplitude and frequency/ damping among the three repetitions. The system starts with a frequency that steadily increases with the decreasing acceleration (and displacement) amplitude as a consequence of the substantial damping ratio decrease and some other possible phenomena (e.g. added mass effect due to the absence of in-vacuo conditions). In the bottom part of the same figure the damping ratio of component 1 is shown as a function of the acceleration amplitude too. It is interesting to first note that significant differences in ζ_1 are seen starting with the very first data point, unlike the amplitudes A_1 . The reason for this is that, in the system identification procedure, A_j represents the amplitude at the beginning of the time bin, while ζ_j is characteristic of the entire two-period bin. While the amplitude A_1 indeed does not change substantially in the first half-cycle of the motion, the damping ratio encapsulates information from the later times where the liquid does have an effect. Since it was found that at least two periods of motion must be considered in order to reliably identify the damping of the first frequency

Figure 10: Amplitude vs normalized time (top), frequencies and damping ratios of component 2 vs component 2 acceleration amplitude (middle and bottom), 50% filling level and dynamically equivalent dry case. Error bars show the variability between test repetitions

component, this is a natural consequence of this type of analysis.

Point **B** in Figure 9 has a different position in the dry and wet cases, since the different decay rates imply the reach of distinct amplitudes at the same time instance. In the 50% fill case, between points **A** and **B** ζ_1 is bounded in a relatively narrow region, while after point **B** it decreases quasi-linearly. Similar damping trends were observed in 1dof experiments [4], regions of constant damping ratio characterising the violent vertical sloshing region R1. Single degree of freedom experiments also indicated that the damping ratio follows a decreasing trend at even larger amplitudes of motion [5]. More in-depth studies are necessary in order to assess if the same phenomena is responsible for the almost constant damping ratio between points **A** and **B** in the case discussed here.

A modulation effect can be seen in all three identified quantities – amplitude, frequency and damping, shown in Figures 6,8 and 9. The identified modulation frequency is f_1 and it appears to be more pronounced in the wet case. This effect is a manifestation of the internal nonlinear dynamics which was already observed in the form of the frequency sidebands shown in Figure 5. This phenomenon can be also observed in the identified higher frequency components. Owing to its presence, at the differing intensity, in both the dry and wet cases, this effect can only be attributed to both structural and fluid-structure nonlinear interactions.

Moving to the higher frequencies, the wet case amplitude of the second component in Figure 10 shows a significant overlap with the dry case over the entirety of the test. In some of the three

Figure 11: Amplitude vs normalized time (top), frequencies and damping ratios of component 3 vs component 3 acceleration amplitude (middle and bottom), 50% filling level and dynamically equivalent dry case. Error bars show the variability between test repetitions

repetitions, this component is eliminated from the wet case signal sooner than in the dry case. However, the final reached amplitudes are similar. The similarity extends to both the frequency and damping ratio variations, indicating that liquid sloshing makes no significant difference in the second frequency component. The component in the vicinity of the second out-plane bending mode is not significantly affected by liquid sloshing for the case analysed here.

The third frequency component (Figure 11) associated with the first torsional mode is significantly more damped in the wet case, but its amplitude is approximately 50% higher than in the dry case as well. Note that the two trailing markers corresponding to the relatively large amplitude values in the dry case are actually from a later time just before the component is eliminated from the signal. While this offers some indication that component 3 may be both more excited and more damped in the 50% filling level sloshing case, supplementary tests focused on the torsional mode are needed in order to fully assess the phenomenon.

Finally, Figure 12 shows the highest frequency component. Component 4 is largely unaffected by the sloshing, the dry and wet trends being similar in amplitude, frequency and damping. Note the duration of this component, spanning an amplitude range of approximately 10g in a third of the first bending mode period. This component is highly transient and also dominant in the first part of the signal immediately after step release. In order to emphasize the relative amplitude of each frequency component, all amplitudes are shown together as a function of the time parameter in Figure 13. The highest frequency signal component A_4 has the highest

Figure 12: Amplitude vs normalized time (top), frequencies and damping ratios of component 4 vs component 4 acceleration amplitude (middle and bottom), 50% filling level and dynamically equivalent dry case. Error bars show the variability between test repetitions

amplitude, with the mean amplitude value approximately 70% higher than the first component. Almost immediately after the release event, however, the frequency component dominated by the first out-plane bending mode has the highest amplitude, as expected. All other components are damped at various rates according to their respective characteristics such that, after approximately 3.5 periods of motion, only component A_1 is left. The times at which each component is completely eliminated from the acceleration signal varies among the three repetitions. The minimum time is being shown here because this is necessary for the calculation of the error bars.

4 DISCUSSION

The liquid sloshing-induced trends observed in Section 3 can be better understood in conjunction with an analysis based on the visually observed sloshing patterns. As explained in Section 2, two high frame rate video cameras were used in order to observe the liquid sloshing from the side and top of the tank. Examples of video frames from one 50% filling level representative test are shown in Figure 14 at the selected time instances expressed as multiples of the period of oscillation of the first bending mode. Three guiding acceleration values are also provided for each snapshot, indicating the first component's amplitude at the corresponding location using the three tank accelerometers as shown in Figure 1 (root, mid and tip). The tank is oriented here with its outboard end towards the left.

It was noted, in relation to Figures 8 and 9, that the amplitude A_1 is the same for the dry and wet

Figure 13: Amplitude comparison for the four tank tip acceleration components, 50% filling level

cases in the first half-period of the transient motion. Figure 14 now offers a visual interpretation to this result. The liquid starts from a standstill configuration at $t=0$ and then, following the release event, it starts moving together with the structure upwards; only between $t = T/2$ and $t = T$ does the liquid start moving substantially upwards relative to the tank and starts impacting the ceiling of the tank. The sloshing force acting on the tank was, in the past studies, isolated and shown to be correlated with the movement of the liquid relative to the tank in harmonically-excited systems [6]. A single degree-of-freedom system with the sloshing liquid and undergoing a free transient vibration exhibits qualitatively and quantitatively different behaviours depending on the combined fluid-structure response characteristics. It was shown in [4] that there are the following sloshing-induced damping regions in certain excitation ranges: R1 - the most dissipative regime, described by the vertical violent sloshing with impacts between the liquid and the top/ ceiling of the tank; R2 - region characterised by the well-defined fluid motion in one of its sloshing modes with possible occasional impacts with the top of the tank, characterised by the dissipation rates still much higher than those of the underlying dry system. A transition region R2&R1 was also shown in [6] where both effects contribute depending on the amplitude of excitation. In regard to the vertical accelerations for these regimes, it was generally observed that at least $1g$ is needed to excite significant free-surface motion such that substantial and repeated impacts with the tank ceiling occur. Depending on the geometry of the tank, liquid sloshing modes can be excited at lower amplitudes as well, promoting thus more energy dissipation. All of these phenomena can be observed in the present case as well.

The individual tank cells are numbered from 1 to 8, starting from the root's end (right hand side in Figure 14). The peak accelerations of component 1 at the root-end of the tank do not exceed $1g$. Small surface ripples in cells 1 and 2 are seen to develop in time but their amplitude is likely not large enough to contribute to any substantial dissipation in the system. There is a noticeable difference between cells 2 and 3 in what concerns the observed sloshing patterns, since the cell geometry changes substantially as well (see bottom section of Figure 1). Moving towards the middle section of the tank, cells 3 and 4, vertical accelerations of up to $3.3g$ are reached there. After approximately 2 periods of motion, the sloshing in these cells evolves to start hitting the top of the tank. Liquid motions are dominated by the (2,0) sloshing mode at a frequency of $F1/2$, as can be seen from the near-periodicity of the sloshing pattern in cells 3 and 4 corresponding to the two full tank periods. This liquid behaviour corresponds to Faraday waves combined with the fluid impacting at the top of the tank (region R2&R1). A similar behaviour was observed in the single degree-of-freedom harmonic excitation tests [6]. It is seen here as the substantial contributor to the sloshing-induced dissipative effects.

The gradient of the vertical accelerations increases further towards the tip-end of the tank (left

Figure 14: Selection of video captures for one representative 50% filling level test. Local acceleration for the first vibration component shown (left: tank tip)

hand side in Figure 14) where the maximum accelerations of 5.5g are reached. The acceleration gradient causes the liquid sloshing motion to be increasingly more violent as we move from cells 5 to 8. This violent vertical behaviour is observed up to $t = 9T$ in cell 8 followed by only occasional roof impacts afterwards. These motions are typical of the most dissipative region R1. Also, since these violent sloshing patterns are localised predominantly outboard, the sloshing force has a larger moment arm relative to the root, likely maximizing the dissipative influence of the sloshing liquid. This hypothesis will be further tested in the future supplementary tests.

Finally, for all of the sloshing regimes observed here, the liquid causes substantially more energy dissipation in the first out-of-plane bending vibration mode, where the values of ζ_1 , shown in Figure 9, are higher compared to the equivalent dry case throughout the entire excitation range. These initial insights lead to the following observations and future research directions:

- The spanwise location of the fuel influences the vertical sloshing regimes. Previous single degree-of-freedom studies indicate substantial sloshing-induced damping effects that depend on the sloshing regime [4,6]. There is thus indication that, depending on the available amounts of fuel, the net damping following the excitation similar to the step release (such as a discrete gust) may be increased by moving the liquid to the specific spanwise positions, taking into account the filling level as well. Supplementary investigations are planned in order to further assess such effects.
- Liquid sloshing patterns dominated by sloshing mode (2,0) are prominent in tank cells 3 and 4 and persistent even at the lowest amplitudes of excitation. Such sloshing modes are highly dependent on the geometry of the tank and filling level and they have previously been observed to add substantial additional damping at lower amplitudes. There exists thus the possibility that the geometry of the fuel tank could be tailored to promote such sloshing patterns and hence achieve increased the sloshing-induced damping.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A scaled research prototype model was presented, representative of the static and dynamic behaviour and the geometry of an airliner wing. The experimental rig was equipped with a transparent fuel tank and was loaded vertically and released, aiming to achieve the conditions similar to the loading experienced by the aircraft wings during the discrete gusts encounters. The focus of this work was placed on the comparative analysis between the 50% filling level case using tap water as the working liquid, and the dry case with the added equivalent liquid mass. The freely decaying response of the system was measured at the multiple points using accelerometers and three measurement points across the fuel tank were used for the analysis.

A piecewise linear model based on the NLS system identification algorithm was used to identify the main frequency components of the dry and wet systems with their associated amplitudes of vibration and damping ratios. Evidence of different types of nonlinearities were shown manifesting themselves as frequency shifts and variations in the damping ratios, induced by the large amplitude vibrations of the dry structure as well as by the sloshing liquid in the fuel tank.

Evidence of substantial additional energy dissipation was shown in the frequency components 1 and 3 associated with the first out-plane bending mode and the first torsional mode. Components 2 and 4 corresponding to higher order out-plane linear bending modes were largely unaffected by the liquid sloshing action for the cases investigated here. The biggest difference when liquid was added was seen in the first frequency component, substantial increase in damping ratio and corresponding decrease in amplitude being evident starting with the second half of the

first cycle of motion. Correlation with previously obtained results for 1dof vertically sloshing systems, as well as video captures from the side of the fuel tank, indicated links between liquid sloshing patterns at various vertical acceleration amplitudes and the induced damping effects. All sloshing regimes noted in reduced-complexity 1dof systems were observed in this study as well, such as violent vertical impacting liquid motions (R1) and lower amplitude Faraday waves (R2) dominated by sloshing mode (2,0). Moreover, the evolution of the observed sloshing patterns with respect to time and local acceleration correlate well with previous transient results.

The experimental results shown in this work represent an initial assessment of some of the tests conducted on the MiniWoT specimen and indicate important liquid sloshing-induced effects manifested in multiple frequency components. The addition of 50% liquid inside the system lead to significantly higher energy dissipation rates. The tests presented here also indicate and fuel planned future directions of study such as the influence of the spanwise position of the liquid, filling level and tank geometry.

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